

ARTICLES

Jarosław PŁACHECKI

Irish Polish Society, Chairman

Old Polish University in Kielce, Dean of the Dublin Campus

Retaining the national identity. 35 years of the Irish Polish Society

Abstract: In 2014 the Irish Polish Society celebrated the 35th anniversary of its foundation. The history of our Society, its link with John Paul II's arrival in Ireland in 1979, and the history of the office of the Society in the Polish House (Dom Polski) at 20 Fitzwilliam Place in Dublin will be the subject of a separate publication edited by Hanna Dowling – secretary of IPS. The current paper is an introduction to the discussion on the history of the Polish community in Ireland and on the role of our Society and other Polish organisations in maintaining the national identity of the Poles in Ireland. On the occasion of 35th anniversary of IPS foundation, the board of the Society organised a special conference *Why are we here: 35 years of the Irish Polish Society*, which took place on 27 September 2014 in a conference room of the Humanities Institute at University College Dublin. The conference provided an excellent opportunity to share ideas, present papers and lectures, and meet representatives of the Polish community in Ireland, as well as academics, diplomats and politicians.

Keywords: Irish Polish Society, the Polish House, national identity, conference in DCU.

Introduction

For Poles 2014 was a year of jubilees. In May we celebrated the 10th anniversary of the accession of Poland to the European Union, in June – the 25th anniversary of democratic transformation in Poland and of the first partially free elections, and in August –

the 70th anniversary of the outbreak of the Warsaw Uprising. For us, who live abroad, the memory of these events has a special value. The events remind us about our national identity and give us an opportunity for talking about them again, and making them known to our fellow countrymen as well as neighbours and friends from the countries in which we have to work and live. Polish community organisations, Polish weekend schools, diplomat posts, Polish parishes and Polish media abroad have engaged in this trend, contributing to popularisation of Poland, its history and achievements all over the world. For many, especially new, organisations it was a sort of organisational debut, which created an opportunity to show off their achievements or even to become known. All these efforts should be given support, direction, and further encouragement. Isn't it the right way of understanding the role of the old deeply rooted emigration (Dowling, 2012: 109)?

Also for Polish community organisations in Ireland, 2014 brought important events and anniversaries. Web portals: Together – Razem, My Cork, Irlandia.ie, Galway.pl, Polski Limerick or POSK have informed us on current and forthcoming meetings, exhibitions, concerts, etc. Recently in Ireland we have also seen an emergence of groups of Polish activists and leaders acting in informal and not yet registered organisational structures, such as: Forum Pomocy dla Bezrobotnych, Polish Community in Ireland, MultiCity Kilkenny, Forum Polonia or Discover Poland, as well as the once created *ad hoc*: Jesteś u Siebie Zagłosuj (JUSZ) and Polish People's Stories. Many of them have not stood the test of time or exploited their potential by the time of achieving their goals (Płachecki, 2012: 138).

Polish weekend schools and associated organisations could boast well-documented educational activity directed at preserving the Polish language among the Polish youth in Ireland; among them were: PSE Dublin, PSE Waterford, Polska Organizacja Oświatowa in Limerick, PilsCork, SEN, PilsCavan, Polska Macierz Szkolna and Federacja Polskich Stowarzyszeń Edukacyjnych EPI. The educational offer for adults included Polish universities acting in Ireland: Społeczna Akademia Nauk in Łódź and Wyższa Szkoła Rozwoju

Lokalnego in Żyrardów. Currently, the only Polish university entitled to provide degree programmes in Ireland is Old Polish University of Kielce, which has a branch faculty here (Campus Dublin). Polish students have an opportunity to get a degree in economics and special education. Classes conducted in Polish take place twice a month at weekends in a building of Business School of Dublin City University at Collins Avenue in Dublin.

An important role in maintaining ties with Poland, the Polish native language, culture, and history is also played by Polish chaplaincy, including especially the church at High Street in Dublin, as well as Dublin chaplaincy 'Dominikanie dla Polaków' and 'Jezuicka Posługa Polakom' in Ireland. A synthetic account of the activity of Polish chaplaincy in Ireland is provided in a book 'Polscy migranci w Irlandii: wokół środowiska duszpasterstwa polonijnego' edited by Marek Grubka and Marcin Lisak.

All these activities undertaken by social organisations, societies, churches, Polish community schools and academic centres have a certain feature in common, namely the fact they all strive after integration with the local people and preservation of the national identity of Poles living in Ireland permanently or temporarily. The methods of realisation of these goals include a range of activity types: educational, religious, self-help, artistic, cultural, and in some cases also political.

Established in 1979, the Irish Polish Society is a Polish organisation with the oldest tradition and a relatively wide scope of activities, promoting integration between the Irish and the Poles while preserving cultural wealth and the identity of both nations (Johnston, 2014: 3). An impetus to a formal creation of the organisation was a historical visit of John Paul II to Ireland that year. The 35th anniversary of the establishment of the Society coincides with 35th anniversary of the papal pilgrimage to Ireland.

Today the Irish Polish Society (IPS) is a dynamic Polish community organisation arranging a variety of cultural and social events for people of any age, such as art exhibitions, musical and literary soirees, book promotion, film screening, talks given by Irish lecturers and Polish visitors, and family picnics. IPS holds an advisory

role in the matters of integration. We cooperate with the Embassy of the Republic of Poland in Dublin as well as Polish and Irish non-governmental organisations. The society celebrates major cultural events and religious festivals important for the residents of both countries (Dowling, 2013: 4). The Irish Polish Society Yearbook, vol. I, 2014 contains a detailed calendar of events either organised by IPS or attended by the Society members in 2013.

Apart from experience gained in the past 35 years, normalising procedures and multispectral range of activities, an essential factor distinguishing the Irish Polish Society from other Polish community organisations is the combination of the cultivation of national tradition with integration. These goals are by no means contradictory, nor mutually exclusive. If we assume that the carrier of culture is language, then the success of such an approach lies in the respect for the cultural wealth of both languages, that is the mother tongue and the foreign one. This can be achieved for example by publishing bilingual bulletins, announcements and letters, which come out in print and on the Internet, as well as by using the principle of bilingualism at important meetings and events. This principle also applies to our books and periodicals, including the Irish Polish Society Yearbook. As in other European countries, which face migration on a massive scale, the growing tendency to lose national identity among the youth is not a new phenomenon. The problem has also affected Ireland, which for historical reasons has almost lost its national language in favour of the English one.

Along with integration processes and gradual assimilation, we witness the loss of a sense of national identity and gradual disappearance of the Polish language skills in speech and writing, as well as cultural absorption. It is a natural and spontaneous process. It concerns the first generation of Polish children, who were born in Ireland, the young who began their education in Polish schools and continued it in Ireland, as well as the adults for whom English is the second language.

In all cases a phenomenon of cultural attractiveness of one language over the other comes into play. As in the case of Irish, which for years has been perceived as a language of the province,

Polish under certain conditions is likely to become not sufficiently attractive for the Polish young people. It may happen especially when their parents keep isolating themselves in 'Polish ghettos' (job-home-job), while occupying low social status positions due to lack of English language skills. In practice, staying away from the native country for a long time may lead to the gradual loss of orthographic and stylistic skills, which in turn may result in functional illiteracy in speech and writing.

An antidote to these problems seems to be treating the mother tongue on an equal footing with the language of the receiving country by children and young people, showing attractiveness of teaching and use of the Polish language as a second language, or business language, as well as learning English by parents as a chance for improvement of the social status of Polish families in Ireland.

Niamh Nestor points to certain practical solutions. The author suggests '... closer cooperation between mainstream and complementary schools in Ireland. Secondly, the Irish government should officially recognise complementary schools and this should be reflected in the legislation. Thirdly, changes should be made to the ways in which teachers' professional qualifications are recognised, particularly those who are qualified to teach non-curricular subject as part of the Irish post-primary school system. Fourthly, exams, e.g. Polish, needs to be reviewed. Currently, the exam does not contain an oral exam or a listening comprehension section; this should be changed' (Nestor, 2014: 50). The above suggestions took the form of recommendations published in May 2014 in a document *Submission on Ireland's National Integration Strategy to the Department of Justice and Equality* presented on 8 September during public consultations at the Office for the Promotion of Migrant Integration (OPMI) and submitted to Aodhán Ó Ríordáin, the Minister of State for New Communities, Culture and Equality in the Polish House (Dom Polski) at 20 Fitzwilliam Place on 19 September 2014.

On the occasion of 35th anniversary of IPS foundation, the Society organised a special conference *Why are we here: 35 years of the Irish Polish Society*. The conference took place on 27 September 2014 in a conference room of the Humanities Institute at University

College Dublin. The languages of the conference were Irish and Polish. Seven papers were presented. They regarded the education of the Polish community in Ireland and anniversary of our society. The topics discussed included:

- Dr John Kearns (ITIA) – The Poles in Ireland in 2004–2014: from a translator's perspective,
- Niamh Nestor (UCD) – The Polish language in Irish schools: Educational reform and the role of supplementary education in Ireland,
- Witold Iżycki (SPK) – Ten years of School Consultation Point at the Embassy of the Republic of Poland in Dublin,
- Dr Bożena Cierlik (UCC) – Polish students in Irish universities,
- Dr Gabriel Doherty (UCC) – Irish Polish relationships: From regaining independence to the fall of communism,
- Hanna Dowling (IPS) – Poles in Ireland, their contribution to the Irish society and the beginnings of the Irish Polish Society,
- Edyta Jankowska (IPS) – Irish Polish Society: current activity and plans for the future.

The official opening was done by Longin Komołowski, the President of the 'Wspólnota Polska' Association. The first part of the conference was chaired by Dr Bożena Cierlik. The programme included a discussion and reading out of a congratulatory letter from Prof. Wawrzyniec Konarski (UJ) by Patrick Quigley (IPS). The second part of the conference was opened and chaired by Dr Jacqueline Hayden (TCD). Our special guests at the conference were: president of the Stowarzyszenie 'Wspólnota Polska' and former PM Mr Longin Komołowski, director of the Stowarzyszenie 'Wspólnota Polska' Iwona Borowska-Popławska, the Minister of State for New Communities, Culture and Equality Aodhán Ó Ríordáin, *Charge d'Affaires* of the Polish Embassy in Dublin Piotr Rakowski and designated Ireland's Ambassador for Poland dr Gerard Keown.

The aim of the conference was the celebration of the 35th anniversary of the Irish Polish Society and an attempt to answer the question: why do Poles in Ireland feel at home and why do they integrate well with the Irish society?

At the conference the participants attempted to give evidence that the Polish language can be attractive to both the Polish community abroad and the foreigners. The key to making this idea work should be an educational, cultural and artistic activity, which, providing that the cultural and historical identity is respected, integrates the Poles with the society of the receiving country with no need to abandon the culture of the native language. While education is a direct method, organisation of cultural, literary and artistic events is a supplementary and supporting activity. The role of the Irish Polish Society and other Polish community organisations in Ireland seems to be invaluable for preserving Polish writing and speaking skills. These activities should be continued, supported and encouraged, both by the Polish and the Irish authorities.

Summary in Polish

W trosce o zachowanie narodowej tożsamości. 35 lat Towarzystwa Irlandzko-Polskiego

W roku 2014 Irish Polish Society obchodziło 35. rocznicę powstania. Historia naszego Towarzystwa, jego związek z przyjazdem Jana Pawła II do Irlandii w 1979 roku oraz dzieje siedziby związku w Domu Polskim przy 20 Fitzwilliam Place w Dublinie będzie przedmiotem odrębnej publikacji przygotowywanej obecnie przez sekretarza IPS, Hannę Dowling. Niniejszy artykuł jest jedynie przyczynkiem do dyskusji nad dziejami irlandzkiej Polonii i roli naszego Towarzystwa, a także innych organizacji polonijnych w utrzymaniu tożsamości narodowej Polaków w Irlandii. Z okazji 35-lecia założenia IPS zarząd Towarzystwa zorganizował specjalną konferencję tematyczną pt. *Dlaczego tutaj jesteśmy: 35 lat Towarzystwa Irlandzko-Polskiego*, która odbyła się 27 września 2014 r. w sali Humanities Institute w University College Dublin. Konferencja stała się znakomitą okazją do wymiany myśli, prezentacji wykładów tematycznych oraz spotkania przedstawicieli Polonii, świata akademickiego, dyplomatów i polityków.

W trakcie konferencji uczestnicy starali się udowodnić, że język polski może być językiem atrakcyjnym zarówno dla Polonii, jak i dla obcokrajowców, a kluczem do tego powinna być działalność edukacyjna, oświatowa, kulturalna czy artystyczna, która przy poszanowaniu odrębności integruje Polaków ze społecznością kraju przyjmującego bez konieczności wychodzenia

z obszaru kulturowego swojego języka ojczystego. O ile edukacja jest metodą bezpośrednią, to organizowanie wydarzeń kulturalnych, literackich czy artystycznych może być działaniem wspomagającym i komplementarnym. Rola Irish Polish Society i innych organizacji polonijnych w zachowaniu umiejętności posługiwania się językiem polskim w mowie i w piśmie wydaje się być nieoceniona. Działania te powinny być kontynuowane i wspierane przez instytucje rządowe zarówno w Polsce, jak i w Irlandii.

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